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Introducing Innovative Processes Into Pedagogical Sciences and Main Directions of its Development

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Abstract: Today, globalization processes in all spheres and the rapid penetration of information require the establishment of systematic management of innovative processes in modern educational institutions, including educational institutions. The article describes the content and essence of the introduction of innovative processes into pedagogical sciences and the main directions of its development.

Keywords: Innovation, pedagogical sciences, technology, education, educational content, educational goal, need, motive, skill qualification.

INTRODUCTION

In all periods of human development, there was an environment of mutual competition. Although the eras of war, violence, and competition at the expense of force have lasted for a long time, new ways of engaging in social, economic, and cultural competition have emerged. Because the level of civilization is gradually increasing due to education, knowledge and learning. From this point of view, the superiority of nations, social groups and individuals over others is based on a new paradigm - innovation.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

A lot of research has been published on the advantages, economic efficiency and social time savings of people and other aspects of the innovative development path. An innovative way of thinking is able to create products and social mechanisms with a high utility coefficient, as above. The inability of the members of the whole society to think innovatively, and the fact that such a way of thinking belongs only to certain social groups and individuals, indicates that the subject is in common with the pedagogical sciences. It's not for nothing. Because in today's fast-paced world, who wins? A country that relies on new ideas, new ideas, and innovation will win. Innovation is the future. "If we start building our great future today, we should start it on the basis of innovative ideas and an innovative approach," said Shavkat Mirziyoyev, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. And innovative thinking is the direction of each subject on the path of development in accordance with his knowledge, knowledge and potential. Whether it is short or long, ineffective or effective, depends on the degree of manifestation of innovative thinking. The current stage of development poses great problems for pedagogical sciences. It is known that the object of the pedagogical process is the most primitive form of imparting certain knowledge to the student in the form of information presentation. Based on the worldview and level of each learner, as well as relying on the skills of the pedagogue, this information is absorbed. For many years, knowledge was passed from generation to generation in this way, and the most important aspect in this process was the monopoly of the pedagogue over this information. That is, only the teacher could deliver the knowledge accumulated over centuries to the student. Now the situation has completely changed. The information age has provided humanity with the opportunity to freely, cheaply and without spending too much resources on complex

issues ranging from simple etiquette to genetics, quantum physics and the most subtle aspects of the human psyche. This led to a change in the social value of the pedagogue, who is the sole owner of knowledge. In this situation, the important issue facing the pedagogue is to select from the general flow of information suitable, useful and interesting information for the learner and deliver it in accordance with his worldview. Such demands caused innovation to enter the sphere of pedagogical sciences. It is clear that the first ideas about innovation were formed in the early stages of human cultural development. Because, whether it is lighting a fire, maintaining a household, preparing food, in any field, someone has come up with a new, different and more efficient way, and this particular way is later called innovation. "Innovation means introducing a new combination of new production factors and production conditions into the production system. It includes five situations: introducing a new product, introducing an advanced production method, opening a new market, and creating a new source of supply of raw materials or semi-finished products.

Technological innovation is technological and economic integration, technological progress and practical innovation," wrote economist Joseph Schumpeter, who introduced the concept of innovation to science. From the point of view of economic benefits, the manufacturer is always in the process of lowering the cost of the product and thereby strengthening its position in the market. This requires saving time, labor and raw materials spent on the product. Usually, a product is already in an optimal shape by the time the prototype is created, and simply reducing the above resources will not reduce them. It is only by introducing knowledge, science and new ideas into this process that it is possible to create a product that has the same appearance and quality as before or even better. Hundreds of subsequent studies and achievements have proven that this is the most correct and effective way, and the research in this regard was considered worthy of the Nobel Prize in Economics. This is how the genesis of pedagogical innovations appeared. The acceleration of information played a decisive role in determining the direction of the future development of pedagogy. Firstly, there is an endless ocean of information in front of the subjects of education, and the pedagogue needs to separate the knowledge necessary for the student from the main existence and direct it to the subject. For this reason, in the late 80s and early 90s, wide-ranging innovative changes began to appear in the theoretical and practical stages of pedagogical sciences, and they are two important - the study, generalization and dissemination of advanced pedagogical technologies; he had to solve the issue of putting the achievements of psychology and pedagogy into practice. As a result of globalization and informatization, it is now easier to spread advanced pedagogical technologies around the world.

This accelerated the spread of modern ways of teaching at a new pace. One of the unique aspects of communication is that audio and video materials are now freely available along with traditional textual information, and this has had a very positive impact on the learning process. Now, the opportunities for professionals and students to get knowledge in a visual way, not in their imagination, have expanded. It is known that Ya. Comensky put forward the concept that the educational process is like a well-functioning mechanism and gives an inevitable positive result. The essence of the classroom system was to provide education on the basis of modern technologies. At this point, the view that technology should perform an important task in the didactic process as a tool in the hand of a pedagogue was put forward. It is as a result of the paradigmatic importance of technologies for pedagogical sciences that innovative approaches to this field began to be felt more clearly. Because the innovative approach is an activity aimed at effectively changing the existing system, not entirely, but partially. We look to Ken Robinson's vision of a new educational paradigm to find out why innovative thinking has been necessary for the last 50 years. According to him, 98% of preschool children have a non-standard, divergent way of thinking. As a result of school education, this indicator decreases to 32%. According to the scientist, it is not only about teachers, but it was intended to raise a generation adapted to standard thinking from the genesis of the educational system.

Because for the last 300 years, the education system was aimed at educating a standard-thinking generation, adapted to use and service the industrial equipment and technical means for the booming industry.

CONCLUSION

This was especially evident in the policy of the Soviet government on socialization and literacy of society members, especially women, along with industrialization. Rapid economic growth requires skilled workers for industrial enterprises, and the training of such personnel is entrusted to the educational system. As the economic changes are undergoing rapid and complex changes, the demand for personnel has been increasing accordingly. This later set the educational system the task of raising a generation with a new, innovative way of thinking.

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